

THE ETHICAL DIMENSIONS OF REWARD-DRIVEN INFORMATION REPORTING

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10260857>

Abstract: Online bounty reporting behavior represents a complex phenomenon emerging within the digital realm, encompassing various information-related actions like human flesh searches, online surveillance, whistleblowing, seeking assistance, and asserting rights. Rooted in a collective moral critique framework, this behavior integrates economic incentives with information-sharing capabilities afforded by cyberspace, encouraging individuals to track, disclose, and take "defensive actions" against acquaintances, culminating in a distinct form of online reporting. This study delves into the intricacies of this behavior, shedding light on its evolution and characteristics within the contemporary digital landscape.

Keywords: online bounty, information behavior, digital reporting, collective moral criticism, cyberspace

1. The background and development of the act of soliciting reported information with bounties in cyberspace

The information behavior reported by online bounty is not an isolated act that appears out of thin air, but based on common types of behaviors such as human flesh search, online supervision, whistleblowing and whistleblowing, and seeking help and rights protection, the factor of civil reward has been added, and it has been further integrated and developed. In the social context of collectivist moral criticism, it takes advantage of the convenient, rapid, and wide coverage of information dissemination in cyberspace, and uses economic interests as an incentive to encourage people to track and disclose the information of others they know and carry out aggressive "defensive actions" against others, thus constituting the online bounty reporting behavior discussed in this paper.

1.1 The social culture of collectivist moral criticism

The rise and evolution of online bounty reporting is inseparable from the social context. In various social and cultural systems, people's motivations and behaviors are influenced by a variety of factors, such as living environment, moral perceptions and legal systems. Traditional cultural cognition is an important part of shaping behavior. China's traditional collectivist culture contains a series of values, beliefs, moral principles and social norms that emphasize collective interests, family relationships, and fraternity and mutual assistance, and highly ethical acquaintance communities will in fact cause a blurring of interpersonal boundaries. The recognition that

"everyone has the obligation to maintain harmony" will subtly shape and influence the way of thinking and behavior of individuals. When individual behavior is seen as a component and obligation of the collective good, people are more likely to pay attention to others, be sensitive to behavior contrary to public ethics, and tend to engage in moral criticism in close relationships, equating this interference with others with contributions to society. Under normal circumstances, criticism and interference are indirect and hidden, in order to avoid the conflict pressure brought by directly putting forward counterarguments, gossip, chewing the root of the tongue, and talking on the street will try to avoid the object of discussion. Since the interpersonal harmony required by the "golden mean" is at the heart of social norms, cultural rules require humility and restraint, and hide strong emotions, inhibit the free expression of negative emotions, and [1]anger and aggression are only publicly justified on a moral basis – understood and supported as good behavior to assume social obligations. Moral criticism, full of anger, has become a breakthrough in the regulation of individual emotions under the pressure of collectivist norms.

1.2 The development context of online bounty reporting information

The integration process of online bounty reporting information covers multiple aspects such as human flesh search, public opinion supervision, and rights protection and evidence collection in cyberspace. First, the rapid development and popularization of Internet technology has given individuals the opportunity to access the network platform at a low cost, use the advantages of data dissemination to spread their voice, and use social media, blogs, forums and other platforms to express their views and views on social issues. They are also able to distribute or publicly disclose the information they have about others. On the basis of extensive affirmative expression, the public has mastered new means of supervising the exercise of power and has gradually become familiar with the process of online appeal, help, disclosure, and accusation. Human flesh search can develop because of its positive social benefits, forming a mass force for anti-corruption, anti-gang crime and cracking down on illegal crimes; in private terms, attracting more people to pay attention to the injustice and infringement encountered by individuals, and increasing the success rate of evidence collection and rights protection.

1.2.1 The Internet expresses spontaneously facilitated human flesh searches

Human flesh search is an act of investigating, tracking, and exposing information about specific individuals through the power of online communities, which is commonly used in situations such as exposing illegal facts and exposing inappropriate words and deeds. In the discussion of moral controversy over hot events, the public shares them instantly through the Internet, setting off a wide dissemination of personal information and private affairs in a short period of time, and evaluating and criticizing the social behavior and values of the protagonists of the criticized events. Doxing provides a way for the public to participate collectively in lynching individuals. It is important to note that the source and form of the content are not necessarily illegal. In more cases, the development of the network society itself has promoted the digitalization and networking of people's social life, and people voluntarily record and upload life fragments, perceptions, and views in the form of graphic information, and establish an idealized social image through self-exposure. These one-sided information about the state of the individual will become "evidence" to piece together the appearance of the characters in the field of moral public opinion in possible human flesh search activities. In a sense, it does confirm the thesis in behavior that "man is the product of his own behavior"[2]. But the behavioral clues here are often one-sided and fragmentary, and they are also rendered and distorted by the personal emotions and attitudes of the observers.

Although "human flesh search" under the control of spontaneous order can be regarded as a social control tool with private relief using law and morality as the yardstick, as a huge democratic practice, it has become a temporary carrier of "common power" to make up for the lack of public relief. [3] However, human flesh search contains characteristics such as unjudged and undecided, spying on curiosity, entertainment and entertainment, and the negative risks are also significant.

1.2.2 Public opinion supervision in online anti-corruption and anti-gang crime work

Online reporting in anti-corruption public opinion supervision is a typical act of collecting information on reports. Since 2015, General Secretary has proposed: "Adhere to no forbidden areas, full coverage, zero tolerance, seriously investigate and deal with corrupt elements, and strive to create a political atmosphere that does not dare to be corrupt, cannot be corrupted, and does not want to be corrupted". Since then, the party has been [4] strictly administered, and the blade has been turned inward. Online social platforms have become the main channels for discovering and exposing the corrupt behavior of Party members and cadres. Leaving the operation of power exposed to the sun is directly reflected in the fact that the performance of duties, property status, words and deeds, hobbies, and interpersonal relationships of public officials are exposed to the search and query of the online public, and anti-corruption has become the main position of legal human flesh search. The privacy authority of public officials is reduced, and the right of public supervision is ceded. The government's recreational behavior of exposing inappropriate words and deeds in officials' private lives online has also changed from passive avoidance to active encouragement, forming a new pattern of "eating melons" anticorruption, with public flesh searches first exposing and hype, and then relay investigation by the Commission for Discipline Inspection and Supervision. Some scholars praised this model of network supervision and anti-corruption, believing that it "has the advantages of pluralistic subjects, all-weather and all-round, fast and efficient, safe and cheap, etc., which is conducive to promoting the investigation and handling of cases of violation of discipline and law, enhancing the initiative of fighting corruption and promoting clean government, and the consciousness of public officials to be honest and selfdisciplined, and helping to open up new channels and new prospects for the construction of party style and clean government." [5]

1.2.3 Rights protection and rewarding evidence collection in dispute litigation

One of the main directions for civil entities to initiate rewards is reflected in the enforcement reward system established to solve the problem of difficult enforcement. In May 2011, the Supreme People's Court issued Several Opinions on Sanctions in accordance with the Law and Circumvention of Enforcement, establishing a property reporting mechanism, which stipulates: "The enforcement court may, on the basis of the application for enforcement of the reward of the person applying for enforcement, issue a reward announcement to the public reporting clues about the property of the person subject to enforcement. Where the property clues provided by the informant are verified to be true and are implemented in place, the informant may be rewarded according to the standard or proportion promised by the applicant for enforcement. The award funds shall be borne by the applicant executor. "Articles 2124 of the Provisions of the Supreme People's Court on Several Issues Concerning Property Investigation in Civil Enforcement, issued in January 2017, stipulate in great detail that the person subject to enforcement does not perform the obligations specified in the effective legal document, and the applicant for enforcement may apply in writing to the people's court to issue a reward announcement to find the relevant handling procedures for finding clues about the property of "Lao Lai": When the person subject to enforcement

fails to perform the obligations specified in the effective legal documents, the applicant for enforcement may apply in writing to the people's court to issue a bounty announcement to find out the assets available for enforcement, and the written application shall specify the amount or calculation method of the bounty, the method of issuing the bounty announcement, and the commitment to voluntarily pay the bounty under specific conditions. After the people's court approves and issues a reward announcement, and the relevant personnel provide clues about the property that the people's court has not yet mastered, so that the claims of the executor applying for the announcement of the reward can be fully realized, the people's court will issue a bounty in accordance with the reward announcement. "[6]For more than ten years, with the blessing of Internet technology, the enforcement of rewards and the execution of clue reporting have gradually become professional, institutionalized and matured, opening up a new market for cooperation between private rights protection and public rights relief. "Bounty hunters" who specialize in tracking down "old lai" can take targeted investigations and tracking activities against other citizens who have no interest in them, and report profits with the information obtained. In terms of moral evaluation, the behavior of the "bounty hunter", that is, the whistleblower, is legitimate and positive, and is welcomed and encouraged by the judicial authorities. [7]

Some scholars look at the operating logic behind the above types of behaviors from the perspective of information regulation tools: information is asymmetric and transferable. Portability means that under certain cost conditions, information sharing, and transmission can be realized, and information transfer under material incentives will form a "siphon effect" of information collection, changing the original pattern of information asymmetry. [8-9]Today's wide-area information retrieval and exchange based on network human flesh search has only exploded in volume, and its essence has not changed. Public and private entities in a situation of lack of specific information purchase information from "insiders" in a specific state of information enrichment, this information transaction model has existed since ancient times, and various variations of information trading activities are also an important part of modern social and economic activities. Bounty reporting is essentially a special information trading system. [5]Its contemporary development, deeply affected by the trend of social networking and dativization, integrates with the phenomenon of online violence, and produces online reward reporting information behavior with the nature of shame and retribution.

2. The definition and characteristics of online bounty reporting information

2.1 Definitions

The act of reporting information on online rewards refers to: In addition to the public security organs issuing reward orders in accordance with law, other public and private entities use the method of publicly publishing civil reward advertisements on the Internet to encourage unspecified members of the public to provide the bounty giver or the competent organ with information related to clues related to specific individuals' ethics, violations of discipline, violations, and crimes. The main content of the information is effective clues or evidence materials that can be investigated for corresponding responsibility, aiming to expose potential violations of discipline, violations, violations, criminal acts or moral improper words and deeds, and trigger corresponding legal accountability and moral condemnation.

2.2 Characteristics

2.2.1 Subjects

The entities that publish advertisements for reporting information bounty are generally private entities, and natural persons, legal persons, and other social organizations of a nature are acceptable. In May 2018, a flight attendant in Henan Province was killed on a Didi hitchhiker, and after the case, Didi used the driver's personal information registered on the platform to offer a reward of one million yuan to the whole society to open up clues and look for criminal suspects, becoming a typical case of private entities publishing criminal content reward advertisements. [10]Some online media used the concept of "wanted" when reporting and forwarding this incident, but from the perspective of the main body, Didi's behavior cannot be called "wanted", but a civil reward advertisement.

Where government agencies or judicial organs publish advertisements for bounty for reporting information outside their own authority, they also form civil legal acts, and will not be automatically transformed into administrative acts or criminal reward orders because of their status.

2.2.2 Purpose and motivation

Exposing potential violations of discipline, violations, violations, criminal acts or moral improprieties, and triggering corresponding legal accountability and moral condemnation is the direct purpose of launching online bounties. This subjective state of moral justice distinguishes the reward for reporting information from the act of "buying murder" for illegal purposes. The motivation behind it is more complex. "Just as the physical world produces a movement from many combined forces, there are many motives that work together to produce a will." [11] The subjective mentality of the subject who initiates the online bounty reporting information must be malicious - objectively speaking, the malice towards the "bad guys" is still malicious. The subjective motive of maliciously pursuing painful torture on specific individuals has set the tone for "cyber lynching" in the act of reporting information on the Internet.

2.2.3 Mode and scope of operation

No matter which platform is uploaded, given the boundless nature of the network, it is equivalent to a "whole network bounty". The highly morally inflammatory content, which aroused the righteous indignation of viewers, was forwarded, transported, and spread to other online platforms in a short period of time. The data push rules will also strengthen the pertinence of communication among users in the same region and the same preference. Among them, it is inevitable that media operators with greater network influence and online opinion leaders with strong public opinion influence [12] will help the wave. Once it becomes a "hot spot" and attracts more netizens with experience in online violence, the behavior pattern will become more complex. "When a group is alienated from an ideal group that claims justice, it will and its ability to commit violence will and be more resolute, thorough, and uncompromising, than any member of the individual." [13]The act of reporting information on the Internet will not be isolated in a single dimension of information flow, it should be seen as a clarion call to inspire a series of online and offline attacks, which may be the beginning of subsequent group violence."

2.2.4 Legal Relationships

In essence, the act of reporting information on online rewards is publishing advertisements for civil bounties, forming a contractual relationship of civil bounties. Citizens can form debts for bounty contracts by unilateral promises. Article 499 of the Contract Part of the Civil Code stipulates that if the bounty holder publicly declares

that he will pay remuneration to the person who completes a specific act, the person who completes the act may request his payment. Using "contract theory", distinguishing between "completing a specific act" and "expressing the intention of commitment", the intention of the

159 of the Ministry of Public Security on July 20, 2020): In order to discover clues of major crimes, recover property and evidence involved in the case, and seize criminal suspects, when necessary, with the approval of the responsible person of a public security organ at or above the county level, a reward notice may be issued. The reward notice shall specify the basic information of the reward target and the specific amount of the bounty. Article 280: Wanted warrants and bounty notices shall be widely posted and may be published through radio, television, newspapers and periodicals, computer networks, and other means.

Bounty advertisement indicates that it is an offer with effective conditions. [14]Under the premise that the bounty giver has the capacity for civil conduct, if the content released to the outside world is not illegal, infringing, or contrary to public order and good customs, the law does not explicitly prohibit it. When the bounty holder publicly issues a bounty announcement on the Internet, the promised bonus and reward will have legal effect, and after some individuals in the unspecified majority complete the bounty content, the bounty party shall perform the contractual obligation and pay the bonus. In the "Didi Million Reward Arrest Incident", although the standards set by the reward advertisement were unclear and the rights and responsibilities were not clear enough, resulting in disagreements in determining that the conditions required for the reward were met, the Zhengzhou Red Cross rescue team, which participated in the salvage and discovered the suspect, still obtained the million-dollar bonus promised by Didi by suing Didi. [15]

It is worth further exploring the following: first, what is the nature of the bounty advertisements with criminal content published by civil entities, and whether they are legal and valid? Second, whether crowdfunding rewards to collect someone's criminal clues, and loose and unspecified groups issuing invitations to the outside world, calling on the public to actively report crimes, can form an effective legal relationship? Third, individuals or organizations openly express that they will "reward" righteous deeds and offer rewards to collect clues and evidence of personal violations and crimes, and the informant will directly hand them over to the competent unit and public security. If the judicial authorities handle it in accordance with the law, can it be contrary to public order and good customs and thus invalid? It will be discussed in the following sections "Restrictions of Current Laws and Regulations on the Behavior of Reporting Information on Online Rewards" and "Ethical Dilemma of Reporting Information on Online Rewards".

2.2.5 Social benefits

The positive side of online reward reporting information is reflected in the awakening and enhancement of social moral awareness and reflected in the echo of the principle of democracy and rule of law. Ideally, the reporting and punishment of the evil deeds of the wicked is supported by intrinsic moral values, is the maintenance of good rules, public order, and legal dignity, and should be recognized and praised by society. Widely collecting criminal clues through the Internet, encouraging, and calling on the public to actively participate in the exposure and resolution of social problems, is conducive to promoting the establishment of a democratic social governance structure, cultivating a sense of social responsibility under the framework of popularizing the rule of law, and transmitting intolerance of illegal acts through the improvement of public participation of the whole people.

3. The ethical dilemma of reporting information on online bounties

Some scholars have pointed out very sharply that the human flesh search in the digital age "traces the eight generations of ancestors and historical issues" is not so much a "vast ocean of people's war" that took place in virtual space, but a repetition of the habitual violent acts of the Cultural Revolution in the online world. [16]The act of reporting information on the Internet not only instigates a large-scale human flesh search in the name of moral judgment, but also adds a material reward incentive to the fanaticism of encircling and suppressing similar kinds. Even if a single occasional online reward reporting information behavior is likely to remain on the moral high ground, and objectively meet the retributive effect of punishing rape and eliminating evil, and bring positive social benefits, the interpersonal attack mode, and the atmosphere of per fidelity and mutual harm formed by it will cause systematic moral collapse and disrupt the social order dominated by the rule of law civilization. After the combination of reward reporting information behavior and network technology, a new type of online lynching is formed, which has high systemic risks, mainly reflected in the following two aspects.

3.1 Lynching of online violence with uncontrollable collateral damages

The core principles of the rule of law are equality and justice, and the civilization of the rule of law requires that punishment not only obey the substantive justice of retribution and effect, but also conform to the procedural justice that protects human rights. This allows the punishment to remain humane despite its cruelty. In online violence, there is no rule to follow for the snooping, discussion, accusation, abuse, sarcasm, and sarcasm inflicted by the group on the individual. Most of them do not meet the threshold for criminalization of online violent crimes in terms of intensity and nature, and the violence is not serious individually, but the concentration of aggression in blind resentment will form a harmful effect of scattered responsibility and difficult to control. In the social environment where collectivist moral criticism prevails, online public opinion supervision and online violence are two sides of the same coin, and the various personal violations incidental to moral criticism expression cannot provide effective remedies by relying on legal norms and regulatory techniques at this stage.

3.1.1 Not objectivity

The initiation of online violence lynching often stems from personal judgment and attitude towards events, which is highly subjective and full of personal emotional factors, so it is easy to misunderstand and misjudge, and it is also easy to be subject to the conceptual cognition of one time and place, and it is biased. With the spread and diffusion of information, more people's subjective attitudes and emotions are involved in the "fact provision" related to the event, and the "truth" pieced together by fragmented comments is mixed with high-intensity anger and anxiety. From the perspective of communication, the information production in the "post-truth" public opinion phenomenon has more emotional transmission functions. Events are constantly deconstructed and reconstructed in many rumors, and netizens can only blindly make decisions and express opinions based on incomplete information - not so much opinions as accusations of individual emotions. Information becomes a vehicle for emotions, or even alienated into emotions themselves. [17]The emotional factors involved in lynching lead to the loss of its objective and fair neutral value, and thus its instrumental value as a legitimate means of retribution under the civilization of the rule of law. Whether in traditional physical space or cyberspace, the bias brought by extreme emotions can lead to blurred and distorted truth, leading to wrongful "conviction" and excessive retaliation.

3.1.2 Not balanced

Online lynching is often carried out by groups targeting individuals, using criticism, abuse, ridicule, and other methods to carry out personal attacks, and to thoroughly question the individual's life experience and private past, and expose and spread. In particular, doxing of whistleblowing information amplifies moral stains and uses them as a devastating "weapon" to target the individual's most important social relationships. Colleagues, classmates, partners, relatives and friends and other interpersonal relationships related to social life are subject to moral criticism and lashing. As symbolic "bad guys", their suffering is deliberately ignored, and their social role is arbitrarily deprived of violence outside the law. Shameful labels lead to marginalized social exclusion and harm the mental health and human dignity of those affected and those closely associated. This kind of harm is disproportionate, unprincipled, there is no balance between crime and punishment, and there is no clear scale of enforcement, but it is guided by the tide of group emotions and the heat of online topics. And will be driven by the psychology of voyeurism, following the crack of privacy exposure to spread to the relationship around the attacker.

3.1.3 Not equality

The rule of law and the protection of human rights require that civil society resolve disputes and pursue accountability through due process of law, whether it is treated by "good" or "bad", with stable, predictable legal procedures and thus equality. The process of digging individuals into private moral trials cannot provide a fixed scope and fixed standard accountability procedures, the degree of exposure of information is random, and the punishment suffered is also random. In different incidents, the wind of public opinion changes rapidly, and the "inappropriate words and deeds" exposed by human flesh searches may have different weights and be subjected to different levels of violent attacks because they are in different hot topics. Taking typical cheating behavior as an example, celebrities cheating, officials cheating, scholars cheating or general members of society cheating, objects with poor behavior, objects with better appearance, or richer objects, what conversations have been in the process of cheating, what videos have been filmed, may affect the rhythm and severity of subsequent event fermentation, anger sensitive points of different classes, and trigger violent attacks of different scales.

Online bounty reporting information is a material incentive to deepen the inequality of privacy exposure in online violence, which means that the bounty giver has recognized the data power contained in online violence and tried to buy bribes in exchange for manipulation of new power. Leverage unobjective, unbalanced, and unequal lynching retaliation against others. This has gone beyond the limits of spontaneous moral criticism in normal public opinion supervision activities and has changed in nature. **3.2 The fallacy of synthesis of moral behavior**

The fallacy of synthesis in the economic realm is: "What is assumed to be true for the part must also be true for the whole; What is considered to be true in parts must also be true in general." [18]To avoid falling into the trap of synthesis fallacy in the social economy, it is necessary to realize that what is beneficial to the individual is not necessarily beneficial to the whole, and the pursuit of maximizing individual benefits may bring about the collapse and collapse of social public interests." The analytical Marxist scholar Jon Elster used modal logic to reinterpret the fallacy of synthesis from a sociological perspective in his 1978 book *Logic and Society* It is pointed out that the fallacy of synthesis is the basis for the two social phenomena of "anti-ultimateness" and "suboptimality". From the perspective of the individual, people act with the belief of pursuing the optimal solution, but after this belief and action converge, they have to face the result of backfire, in order to form "anti-ultimateness"; The

contradiction between individual rationality and collective rationality is irreconcilable, and people generally realize that after the synthesis of the result conflicts with the original purpose, they enter the game process according to their own rational choices, and they all take the maximization of their own interests as the highest principle of economic and political behavior, but they have to accept that the overall result of the optimal allocation of resources cannot be achieved, and the return to the individual itself cannot achieve the maximization of interests, and can only obtain the "sub-optimal state". The conflict between the individual and the collective caused by the fallacy of synthesis always occurs between people's intentions and results, creating a vicious circle." [19]

3.2.1 Network ecological expression of modal synthesis fallacy

In the context of collectivist culture, the phenomenon of online violence in the name of moral criticism is everywhere. The lynching of online violence set off with the highest moral standards, only partially, does have many clearly beneficial social benefits, which is also the source of social benefits of online public opinion supervision. The online reward for reporting information is the "ultimate" practice of pursuing the highest ethical standards in social life. Individuals may have the "rational" illusion that it is the social responsibility of every citizen to punish adultery and eliminate evil, when certain members of society are found to have violated discipline, violations, illegality, criminal acts or morally inappropriate words and deeds. There is no doubt that it is "right" to bravely expose it and to subject it to legal accountability and moral condemnation. If every member of society actively assumes the above social responsibilities and is even willing to spend valuable private resources to promote the realization of the goal, he can obtain widespread, universal, and ubiquitous "rightness", thereby eliminating all false ugliness and creating a perfect utopia. "Anti-finality" is embodied in the systematic moral collapse that runs counter to individual moral demands and the deterioration of tensions in social relations, the wind of whistleblowing is rampant, and the practice of voyeurism is popular, and no one can be left alone in precarious interpersonal relationships. Given the blessings of network and data technology, if we fall into the fallacy of the synthesis fallacy of moral behavior again, the catastrophic consequences will surely far exceed the catastrophe that has occurred in history.

3.2.2 Risk of hazards after synthesis

To a certain extent, the behavior of reporting information on online rewards encourages the atmosphere of interpersonal attacks and breach of trust, leading to an increase in suspicion and hostility in society. In the long river of time and the torrent of history, people are constantly learning to adapt, correct themselves, and catch up with the pace of social development. Most ordinary members of society are subject to a certain nurturing environment and material living conditions, and even if they are "sincere for good", they can only grasp partial moral practices, and cannot withstand the microscope of human flesh search frame by frame. The act of offering rewards to collect individual bad information first needs to initiate and incite human flesh searches, which will inevitably lead to personal information exposure and privacy leakage at the micro level, and may cause personal retaliation, tracking harassment, social exclusion, false reporting and other infringements; At the macro level, the balance between public order and individual rights and interests will be upset, resulting in abstract collective interests devouring real individual human rights.

3.2.2.1 *Giving rise to specific infringements*

People's behavior is not only affected by their personality, but also by different situations and different stimuli, temporarily showing a good side or a bad side. To define an individual's evil deed as a representative of his or her entire personality ignores the complexity of human nature. Perpetuating this absurd hypothesis, when an individual's evil deeds are discovered, it can be defined as a "bad person", and other evil deeds can be further excavated under the premise of the presumption of guilt in order to punish them and make them suffer at the level of social death. This in itself is not the achievement of justice, but the act of interpersonal attack and persecution itself. The malice contained in the act of attack does not change depending on the moral role of the target. Attacks and punishments against individuals relying on one-sided definitions and simplifying perspectives are typical of vigilante reprisals. The targeted, open and arbitrary nature of the reporting information bounty guides the group to target individuals for privacy mining without boundaries, evaluation and discussion, which of course may appear actual evidence of violations and crimes, but in order to obtain clues and evidence, malicious tracking, surveillance, harassment and other collateral injuries are very easy to occur in the process. Due to the existence of material triggers, it is difficult to avoid slanderous and demeaning hints. When the reward amount is large, malicious reports may occur for profit, and after the bounty ferments into a hot topic on the Internet, rumormongering and slander, and false statements may also occur to attract attention. These negative effects appear at the same time and promote each other, resulting in the target of the bounty as an imaginary "evil" becoming the target of "inhuman" attacks, and their personal rights and interests that should be protected by law are overwhelmed by group violence.

3.2.2.2 *Leading to systemic moral collapse.*

When acquiescing in the disclosure of individual reporting information, it is mostly out of consideration of local benefits, and when the power of the rule of law is insufficient to cover significant social injustice, and justice cannot be achieved through due legal procedures for the time being, the individual's human rights are used as sacrifices to appease the irresolvable anger and value conflicts in social problems. Evil deeds should indeed be punished with justice, but individual "bad people" are not a tool for regulating the level of tension in social relations. The punishment of violence against violence for wrongful acts must and can only be accomplished by legal procedures. Those who commit heinous crimes should also be punished with procedures and degrees of punishment, rather than condoned with uncertain and unbalanced lynching reprisals. Online lynching inherits the barbaric and cruel nature of feudal lynching and undermines the underlying logic of rule of law civilization. This kind of destruction is not significant locally, and once it is synthesized, it is difficult to resist the reversal through the coercive force of law - the group violence caused by the simple concept of justice and the legal struggle for the moral high ground may not fall behind.

In addition, considering that those who can obtain personal privacy information and provide doxing search sources are often people who have been related to the bounty individual in the past, have intersected, or even had an intimate relationship. Providing information that is unfavorable to the target of the bounty in exchange for the reward is an abuse of trust and undermines the sincere mutual trust and mutual dependence of people advocated by civilized society. China has had a historical landscape of institutionalized whistleblowing since ancient times, and as early as the Qin and Han dynasties, a vicious custom was formed, transforming the main social contradictions under the feudal imperial rule into internal strife in which the ruling class vied for power and profit.

Exposing whistleblowers makes full use of human weaknesses and activates the dark side of psychology under the suppression of Confucian benevolent culture. The reality that profits can be obtained by exposing others, supplemented by the threat of severe punishment and harsh laws, has led people to "be cautious about themselves and peep into each other, and to discover the secrets of adultery", and can only be afraid to suspect and spy on each other. The [20]bloody massacre of being brutally punished for being exposed and prosecuted has further exacerbated the social atmosphere of suspicion and prevention among people, so that chasing the wind, playing with right and wrong, and fabricating traps have become the norm, and false accusations and concealment of accusations are inevitable.

4. Conclusion

In traumatic social situations that give rise to the urge to lynch retaliation, it is understandable that people feel anger, hatred, disappointment, and anxiety. This intolerance of evil is also an important force that supports the framework of social civilization development and is a valuable light of human nature. However, as the so-called "stone of goodwill paves the way to hell", [21] the pursuit of justice cannot be achieved by convenient and efficient but unjust means, and the eradication of evil cannot be achieved by emotional catharsis of violence. More important than the payment of individual retribution in a momentary event is to establish fair, just, equal and balanced rules for the operation of the rule of law, and on the basis of ensuring basic human rights, weave a dense legal network and systematically deal with illegal and criminal acts that endanger society. The mass violence that occurs in cyberspace has many facets, and with the emergence of people's networked survival in the digital age, its ferocious and destructive characteristics have gradually been revealed. When dealing with new behaviors related to personal rights and interests implemented through network technology and data technology, it is not too cautious to prevent micro-development. Online bounty reporting may effectively harm the "bad guys," but never just the "bad guys." The network environment and data recording are simply tailor-made and enhanced tools for public display and whistleblowing thinking, and once combined with endless harm, they should be strictly prohibited by clear laws and regulations.

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